

B r i F a c e

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Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring method

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D4: Report on critical bridge decks scenarios and strengthening schemes

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- 1. Description of the most representative typologies of reinforced concrete bridge decks.**
- 2. Description of the causes of concrete bridge decks' deterioration/pathologies.**
- 3. Description of the strengthening schemes for bridge decks (technique, type, advantages, disadvantages, control, recovery contribution).**

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Typologies of bridge decks:

Table 1 shows the most common met typologies of bridge decks:

- a) Solid Slab (1-2),
- b) Waffle slab (3),
- c) Voided Slab (5),
- d) Beam and Slab (4) and
- e) Box Girder (7-9).

Each one has different advantages and disadvantages and are selected based on different criteria, among which are: i) the span, ii) the cost, iii) type of bridge, iv) exposure conditions, v) traffic loads.

Table 1: Typologies of concrete bridge decks

A/ A	Bridge deck	Description	e.g.
1.			
https://www.indiamart.com/proddetail/solid-slab-bridges-19894712112.html (accessed 07/2021)			
2.			
https://www.linkprojekt.eu/pedestrian-bridge-over-d48-frydek-mistek/ (accessed 07/2021)			
3.			
https://pci-projects.interactivetwist.com/project/little-cedar-creek-waffle-deck-bridge/?search=%2Fproject-profiles-pci-pc%2F&pctemplate=one_column_pc (accessed 07/2021)			
4.			
https://depakmuniraj.blogspot.com/2011/06/psc-girder-bridge-construction.html (accessed 07/2021)			

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5.

voided slab

Kuwait

<https://www.international-engineering-consultants.com/voidedSlabBridges.php?lang=en> (accessed 07/2021)

6.

double tee slab (voided or not)

York, Maine, bridge

https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Double_tee (accessed 07/2021)

7.

box girder

Underneath the No. 2 Road Bridge in Richmond, British Columbia, Canada

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Richmond,_British_Columbia (accessed 07/2021)

8.

double box girder

PR-181 BRIDGE, San Juan, Puerto Rico

<https://www.systraibt.com/en-projet/pr-181-bridge> (accessed 07/2021)

9.

parabolic box girder

Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

<https://www.systraibt.com/en-projet/riyadh-metro-line-3> (accessed 07/2021)

2. Description of the causes of concrete bridge decks' deterioration/pathologies: Nowadays, the existing infrastructure stock of which the average bridge is 50-70 years old phases problems concerning maintenance [42], [47], [46], [50], [51]. The bridge owners are dealing with a large number of structurally and functionally deficient bridges which are in need for upgrading [43]. Given the importance of those structures as well as the resources spent over the years, the repair and strengthening are inevitable. There is a special focus on criteria such as the safety, continuity of use, and above all, failure prevention the following factors are taken into consideration throughout the life-cycle of a bridge so the functionality and structural capacity is assessed (Figure 1):

1. Increase in the traffic load and intensity (overloading, extreme seismic events),

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2. Concrete damages (cracks) and loss of steel cross section due to environmental attacks e.g. steel reinforcement corrosion, chloride ingress, freeze/thaw action, deicing salts carbonation, water ingress
3. Damage due to collision,
4. Damage (cracking) due to fatigue,
5. Changes in the design codes,
6. Inappropriate aggregate consistency e.g. Alkali Aggregate Reaction (AAR),
7. Deviations/errors in construction e.g. poor construction quality, stray electrical current, inadequate steel coatings,
8. Additional safety requirements,
9. Improving traffic conditions e.g. widening of the bridge deck,
10. Structural changes/displacements, extreme phenomena and events, climate change, e.g. creep and shrinkage, seismic events, scour, vibrations, increased thermal exposure, floods.

a) seismic loads- 1994 Northridge Earthquake b) corrosio cracks- Lodi bridge, Italy [46]

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c) collision (Archive Prof. A.I. Karabinis)

d) bridge failure due to scour

e) cracking of the base of a pylon (Bourgogne bridge: crack width >0.3 mm)

f) longitudinal cracks in the middle of a prestressed precast concrete beam

g) concrete spalling

h) leaching/ efflorescence [43]

i) structural cracks

j) expansion joint failure due to temperature variations

Figure1: Typical damages to bridge decks

10. Life cycle issues and independencies with other urban projects,

11. Resources.

A comprehensive study (T1406 Cost Action) includes all the important aspects for strengthening and maintaining existing bridges [42]. Table 1 summarizes all the existing strengthening techniques and types (ADD figure) available for retrofitting all the structural members (e.g. beams, piers, decks) for different reasons (e.g. shear, flexural, torsional strengthening), listing their advantages and disadvantages.

The decision of strengthening technique and strategy is strongly based on the technical feasibility of the bridge reinforcement scheme. Towards this direction the following are considered [48]:

- The technology advancement of the strengthening method/material;
- The acceptance/verification of the measure/technology by engineering practice, industry and international codes/regulations;

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- Difficulties/ limitations/ complexity in the application of the measures;
- The design of the strengthening scheme targets in being suitable for the retrofitting target and satisfying the requirements of the asset to be retrofitted. Hence, it should meet the functional and structural requirements of the bridge, including resistance (strength, flexural, shear, torsional), ductility, stiffness, stability, dynamic response, durability (exposure conditions), compatibility with substrate (bonding of old and new material) and disturbance of the existing response/geometry/function.

Lately, especially with the introduction of the new components of resilience in the modern mindset of asset and network management (response, absorb, recover, adaptation) [44] the proposed scheme should be advanced in technology and simple in application, permitting at the same time fast recover and ideally undisrupted traffic/use during the intervention works (Table 1(8)). **The allocated resources and economic rationality of the bridge strengthening scheme also contributes to resilience.** The cost and duration of the structural strengthening scheme should be kept optimal and should also take into consideration the maintenance costs/resources for future response.

A lot of attention has been given to the strengthening schemes using Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRPs). FRPs, except for the high performance and resistance, are also cost-effective materials compared to conventional construction materials such as steel and concrete, especially considering maintenance costs. Durability matters, in some cases, provide enough benefit to make composites a better choice compared to steel and concrete. FRPs are designed and manufactured to resist chemical corrosion and high temperatures. There are many available protection and coating solutions that help extend the life and protection of the structural element strengthened with FRP components. The efficiency of the strengthening measure and each FRP strengthening system is a matter of question. Each strengthening system exhibits different kind of premature/ dominant failure (Table 1(9)) which is out of the scope of this report.

It is also worth noticing the environmental impact of the FRPs material. The green aspect/dimension lies on the energy consumption to produce FRP composites is lower than that for traditional construction materials such as steel and concrete. Also, it is possible to recycle the FRP materials. FRPs can be crushed and granulated. The granulated material can be used as filler, reinforcement and lately they have been used in railways.

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Table 2- Summary of Bridge Strengthening Techniques

A/A (1)	Strengthening Scheme (2)	Type (3)	Advantages (4)	Disadvantages (5)	Strengthening/control (6)	Retrofitted member (7)	Retrofitting materials (8)	Recovery contribution (9)	Dominant failure (10)
1.	Externally Bonded FRP (EB FRP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> plates sheets strips wraps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high strength to weight ratio⁴ ease and speed of application⁴ high corrosion resistance⁵ good bonding with epoxy-based adhesives³ undisrupted asset's operation⁴ enhancement of ductility in confinement solutions²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> low temperature resistance² high cost of epoxy resins² impractical wet application² impractical application during low temperatures² poor vapor permeability² incompatibility of epoxy resin and concrete² difficult damage detection and assessment on concrete substrate² premature peeling / delamination⁵ requires surface preparation²⁰ unprotected FRP Material against wear, fire and impact loads²⁰ bond affected by aggressive environmental conditions²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flexural⁵ shear²⁰ compression-confinement⁵ torsional⁵ crack⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> glass (GFRP) carbon (CFRP) aramid (AFRP) basalt (BFRP) steel (SRP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> upon adhesive application, it is recommended the strip be left undisturbed for 24 hours and the structure not used for a week²⁸ application can be done without disruption of traffic⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> concrete cover separation/peeling interfacial debonding
2.	Mechanically Fastened FRP (MF FRP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bars strips rods fasteners threaded bolts expansion anchor bolts power-actuated fasteners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high strength to weight ratio⁴ prevents from premature peeling/delamination⁵ allows easier FRP post-tensioning⁵ surface preparation not required²⁸ ease and speed of application²⁸ good temporary measure due to reversibility²⁹ installation requires common hand tools³⁰ can be performed by unskilled labour³⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> anchors susceptible to corrosion¹⁸ less economical vs steel PT anchors¹⁸ complicated installation¹⁸ fastened joints exhibit stress concentrations¹⁹ significant slip at concrete-FRP interface²⁹ fasteners may damage concrete substrate³⁰ requires significant drilling³⁷ danger of galvanic corrosion of internal reinforcement if fasteners are in contact with steel³⁷ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flexural³⁷ shear torsional crack 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> glass (GFRP) carbon (CFRP) aramid (AFRP) basalt (BFRP) steel (SRP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> immediate use of the retrofitted structure²⁸ minimizing traffic delays, safety hazards, and financial losses³⁷ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> tensile yielding & concrete crushing³⁷ concrete cover separation/peeling³⁷ bearing failure of the FRP around the interior fasteners and end anchors³⁷
3.	Near Surface Mounted FRP (NSM FRP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bars strips 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high strength to weight ratio⁴ little repair material required¹⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> decreases ductility¹⁹ debonding failure¹⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flexural⁶ shear 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> glass (GFRP)⁶ carbon (CFRP)⁶ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> debonding/pull-out of rods³⁸

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cost effective¹⁹ less prone to premature failure¹⁹ better protection of FRP material against wear, fire and impact loads¹⁹ good durability¹⁹ good fatigue performance¹⁹ high bond efficiency vs EB FRP⁶ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> requires groove preparation¹⁹ decreases moment redistribution behaviour¹⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> compression²⁰ crack¹⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> aramid (AFRP) basalt (BFRP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> concrete cover separation/peeling³⁸ 	
4. Fibre Reinforced Cementitious Matrix (FRCM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> various configurations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> high temperature resistance¹ possible applications on wet surfaces¹ possible applications during low temperatures¹ compatible with concrete substrate¹ good vapor permeability¹ easy substrate (concrete) damage assesment²⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> low bond efficiency due to mortar-based adhesive which are less effective vs epoxy resins³ poor impregnation of fibre sheets² premature debonding³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flexural¹ shear¹ compression/Confinement¹ torsional¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> glass (GFRP)¹ carbon (CFRP)¹ aramid (AFRP)³ steel (SRP)¹ Phenylene Benzobis Oxazole (PBO)¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> debonding of the internal matrix layer³⁹
5. Sprayed FRP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> short randomly oriented chopped fibres polymer matrix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> avoids unidirectional composite material¹⁷ suitable for complex surfaces, geometries & joints¹⁷ forms a continuous strengthening layer¹⁷ enhanced bonding vs EBFPR¹⁷ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> quality control issues of mixing the fibres and resins⁴⁰ requires surface preparation¹⁷ practical limitations in fibre placement around sharp corners²¹ premature debonding²¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flexural⁵ shear²¹ compression/confinement⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> glass (GFRP)²⁰ carbon (CFRP)²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> fracturing and debonding of FRP⁴⁰ concrete crushing and yielding of steel⁴⁰
6. Steel Plate/Brackets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> steel Plate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> potential enhancement of beam ductility²³ ease of application²³ increase member stiffness⁸ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> increase in selfweight²⁵ undesirable change in stiffness²⁵ higher weight to strength ratio²⁵ debonding⁸ required handling heavy parts²⁵ corrosion of plates²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flexural⁸ shear⁸ compression/confinement²⁰ torsional 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> steel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> no traffic disruption²⁷ short construction period²³ possible application under traffic loads²³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> debonding of steel plate⁸ diagonal tension failure beams suffering from corrosion⁸
7. External Post Tensioning (Steel strands)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ease of inspection⁹ speed of installation⁹ cost effective⁹ low increase in deadload¹¹ tendons can be replaced / restressed¹⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> tendons susceptible to corrosion¹⁰ prestress force decreases over time¹² requires concrete in good condition¹¹ difficult Anchorage installation¹¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> deflection²⁰ crack control¹¹ flexural¹¹ shear¹¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> beams²⁰ decks²⁰ piers²⁰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> steel strands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> low disturbance to traffic flow⁹ minimum disruption to existing structure⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> crushing of concrete^{9,11}

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • shear capacity difficult to determine¹¹ • potential ductility reduction¹¹ • aesthetics¹¹ 						
8.	Concrete Section Enlargement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • jackets • sleeves 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improves stiffness of member³¹ • ease of application³¹ • enhanced ductility^{32,33} • high temperature resistance³³ • improved durability³³ • good compatibility with concrete substrate³³ • does not change the predominant failure mode³² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • interface slip reduces composite action²² • Increase geometry and member size²⁰ • requires formwork²⁰ • requires surface preparation²⁰ • additional dead load³³ • increased section reduces headroom for bridges crossing roadways 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural³³ • shear³³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams³³ • decks • piers³¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concrete 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural failure with steel yielding and concrete crushing³²
9.	Additional Supports*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reduces the span length and maximum positive moment²⁷ • attractive method for upgrading bridge traffic load capacity by widening^{34, 35} 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • disturbance of the conditions directly below bridge²⁷ • all members require assessment of their capacity to support new load path²⁷ • cost effective with medium to long span bridges thus prohibitive for most short length bridges²⁷ • time consuming construction work³⁴ • use of complicated foundation and use of heavy equipment • expensive³⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural³³ • shear³³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concrete 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -
10.	Providing continuity*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reduces positive moments at mid-spans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduces negative moments at connections • requires removal of existing concrete to place negative reinforcement therefore costly construction • traffic disruption due to construction • post-tensioning connection also costly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flexural • shear 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • beams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • post-tensioning tendons • self-stressed concrete 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • steel • - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -

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